

THE IMPORTANCE OF VOCABULARY IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Annotation: Vocabulary is the most important part of learning a foreign language. Without learning words and building vocabulary all effort to improve a foreign language will be useless. It would be a mistake to think that new words can be easily remembered without regular learning. This article is devoted to highlight the importance of teaching vocabulary. Nobody can deny that increasing vocabulary is an essential part of our life and realizing its importance in language acquisition is a key to academic success in language learning. In addition to this, without vocabulary knowledge any language skill cannot be developed. Teaching vocabulary plays a pivotal role in the learning of a new foreign language and increasing word knowledge is a dynamic and meaningful way to develop it.

Keywords: vocabulary, receptive vocabulary, productive vocabulary, word knowledge, demonstration, explanation, discovery, check question, presentation, comprehension skills.

English is very important to be learnt especially for students, as it is used in almost aspects of life for example economy, science, technology, business, etc. So, people can't deny that the use of English is more and more important recently. Today English is taught in institutions or schools as one of the subject matters.

In teaching English, there are four skills that should be mastered by students. They are listening, speaking, reading and writing. There are many elements should be mastered to support those skills such as vocabulary, pronunciation, structure etc.

The mastery of vocabulary is important to support the four language skills. Coady states that vocabulary is central to language and critical importance to the

typical language learner [2]. A good store of word is crucial for understanding and communication.

Cross states that major aim of most teaching programmes is to help students to gain a large vocabulary of useful words [3]. According to Virginia someone can be said mastering vocabulary if he knows the meaning of the words and knows how to put them together in the sentences [7]. Teaching vocabulary to students is important to prepare them to get the four language skills. Unfortunately, many students do not master vocabulary appropriately.

According to Nation “There are two kinds of vocabulary. They are perceptive and productive vocabulary. Receptive vocabulary refers to the words that native speakers and foreign learner recognize and understand but hardly ever use, it is used passively in either listening or reading. Productive vocabulary is utilized actively either in speaking or writing” [6]. Listening vocabulary is generally larger than his speaking vocabulary while his reading vocabulary relatively larger than his writing vocabulary. Therefore, it can be concluded that vocabulary can be presented in four units. They are reading vocabulary, listening vocabulary, speaking vocabulary and writing vocabulary. Reading vocabulary consists of the word found by people when they are reading. Listening vocabulary is the words that people hear and understand when they are talking to other or listening to radio and television. Speaking vocabulary includes the words people used in their daily life and conversation. The last is writing vocabulary that consists of the word people use in writing essays, reports, letter, etc.

In relation to kinds of vocabulary, Nation stated that there are four kinds of vocabulary in the text:

1) High frequency words. These words are almost 80% of the running words in the text;

2) Academic words. Typically, these words make up about 9% of the running words in the text;

3) Technical words. These words make up about 5% of the running words in the text;

4) Low frequency words. These are the words of moderate frequency that did not manage to get into the high frequency list. They make up over 5% of the words in an academic text [6].

Teaching vocabulary is not easy to do. Some people think that vocabulary teaching only wastes the time because vocabulary number is unlimited. The English teacher had better teach English vocabulary first than other aspects of this language, such as grammar, speaking, reading and writing. Of students know more about vocabulary, it will easy for them to learn another aspect of English language. The teacher needs a good preparation before teaching vocabulary in the classroom. Depending on the teaching goal, a teacher is required to have knowledge about what words to be taught.

Some technique for teaching vocabulary that is summarized as follows:

1) Demonstration - The teacher demonstrates the language where she/ he want the students to study by offering them there in action.

2) Explanation - The teacher explains the construction of language in diagram, using text book, using board.

3) Discovery - The students can be encouraged to understand new language form by discovering them in a text or by looking at grammatical evidence in order to work out a grammar rule.

4) Check Question - The teacher can check question to see if students have understood the meaning and use in the text or paragraph.

5) Presentation - The teacher shows the thing and does not present words to students, for example: pictures, video and also use the mime, action, and gesture to presents the words.

The importance of vocabulary can be shown by its influence on the comprehension skills. The more word knowledge increases on students, the more their comprehension skills get better. But, if they do not pay attention to their

vocabulary growth, they cannot increase the ability on themselves to understand key points of a text which can lead to difficulty in comprehension.

“When a student demonstrates difficulty in recalling key details such as the plot of a story, character names, and settings, it becomes an evident that the student lacks foundational literacy experiences. Furthermore, background knowledge is an indicator of likeliness that students are able to connect to a text” [2]. Thus, the relationship between vocabulary and comprehension reinforce the need for supporting preservice teachers in identifying pedagogical practices and strategies that will increase students’ word knowledge through vocabulary instruction” [1]. Word knowledge is not only needed to develop comprehension skills, but also it is the foundation to the literacy as well. That’s why teachers should pay close attention to this when they teach beginners. But these things are also different in all learners. Additionally, it highly depends on the age of the learner, whether they are adult or children. Teachers should include these psychological things in language acquisition.

The specificity of any individual’s vocabulary knowledge depends on the person and his motivation, desires, and need for the words [5]. Vocabulary mastery refers to the great skill in processing words of a language. It is an individual achievement and possession. For that reason, the biggest responsibility in increasing the knowledge is in the individual himself. The success in widening the vocabulary mastery requires their own motivation and interest on the words of a language.

Many learners have been facing with some problems in language learning for centuries and almost all of these problems related with vocabulary knowledge. The core skill of the language is having a good word knowledge and learning word structure. Although there is not any exact strategy that says it can help 100 % to teach vocabulary to the students, many researchers have conducted several ways such as multimedia, encyclopedias, websites and so on. But the researchers also mentioned that the ways or strategies would be different for different learners.

From the definition above, we can conclude that vocabulary mastery is an individual's great skill in using words of a language, which is acquired based on their own interests needs and motivation. Vocabulary mastery plays an important role in the four language skills and it has to be considered that vocabulary mastery is one of the needed components of language. It highly depends on the student, especially, to the learners' characteristics such as their age, level of education, and what kind of learner they are. Including all of these things below, before teaching vocabulary, the teacher or the learner should identify these things on the students or on themselves. The most important thing is realizing the importance of learning vocabulary, then they can act in the right way which lead them to the academic success. It doesn't matter what level learners' English is, they should never stop learning new words. The more words they know, the more easy they can express their thoughts. They should write down every new word they don't know and memorize it. And they should keep building up their own vocabulary and repeat all the words they know as often as they can.

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